

**Global Geoparks Network
SDG Working Group**

UNESCO Global Geoparks Actions on SDG's in 2023

UNESCO Global Geoparks Actions on SDG's in 2023 2023 REPORT

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UNESCO Global Geoparks and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) of the Agenda 2030

SDG	Main SDG objective	How UNESCO Global Geoparks contribute to the SDGs	SDG	Main SDG objective	How UNESCO Global Geoparks contribute to the SDGs
1 NO POVERTY	End poverty in all its forms everywhere	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Disaster risk reduction programmes & preparation for local communities in your UNESCO Global Geopark (1.5) Activities to support local economy in your UNESCO Global Geopark 	10 REDUCED INEQUALITIES	Reduce inequality within and among countries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Special UNESCO Global Geopark programmes for integration of refugees (10.7) Employment of foreign skilled workers
2 ZERO HUNGER	End hunger, achieve food security and improved nutrition and promote sustainable agriculture	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Support of sustainable agriculture in your UNESCO Global Geopark like family business, small farmers, fishermen, pasture farming (2.3, 2.4) Protection of regional and historic plants and animals (2.5) Regional food programmes 	11 SUSTAINABLE CITIES AND COMMUNITIES	Make cities inclusive, safe, resilient and sustainable	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Accessibility for all in your UNESCO Global Geopark facilities (e.g. trails, information centres, museums...) (11.7) Cooperation with UNESCO World Heritage Sites and other UNESCO programmes inside the UNESCO Global Geopark (11.4)
3 GOOD HEALTH AND WELL-BEING	Ensure healthy lives and promote well-being for all at all ages	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Support of your UNESCO Global Geopark activities for health and well-being in nature: Sports activities (hiking, cycling...) (3.8) Awareness and mental health (e.g. shinrin yoku) (3) Nature health actions 	12 RESPONSIBLE CONSUMPTION AND PRODUCTION	Ensure sustainable consumption and production patterns	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Support of local producers and local products Programmes and activities with local farmers in your UNESCO Global Geopark (12.1, 12.2) Implementation of local markets with regional and seasonal products to create awareness to live in harmony with nature (12.8) Use of local and regional food for own Geopark activities, festivals and events Use of Geopark product criteria and label Support of waste prevention (12.5)
4 QUALITY EDUCATION	Ensure inclusive and quality education for all and promote lifelong learning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Your UNESCO Global Geopark educational programmes from kindergarten up to post-graduate level, as well as University students and programmes of lifelong learning (4.1, 4.2, 4.3) Education on Earth heritage and its links to natural and cultural heritage. Educative tools, trails and publications Education of the SDGs (4.7) Education of staff, guides & stakeholders Inclusive education for all (4.5) 	13 CLIMATE ACTION	Take urgent action to combat climate change and its impacts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Activities of your UNESCO Global Geopark for climate protection: Tree planting, bog waterlogging, unsealing of soils / soil protection Climate protection awareness rising campaigns (13.3) Campaigns to save CO2 (e.g. walking day, public transport) Programmes for resilience against natural disasters and climate induced dangers (13.1) Compensation of CO2 consumption (e.g. plane travelling to conferences etc) either in Geopark territory or compensation programmes (e.g. Atmosfair)
5 GENDER EQUALITY	Achieve gender equality and empower all women and girls	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Gender equality in your UNESCO Global Geopark management team Equal payment of male and female team members Female leading position in the team (5.5) Training courses for women empowerment Support of women cooperatives in the region Special offers for girls (e.g. Mountain Biking, MINT programmes) 	14 LIFE BELOW WATER	Conserve and sustainably use the oceans, seas and marine resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Activities of your UNESCO Global Geopark to protect life under water Cooperation with institutions, which protect marine environment (14.4) Support of sustainable traditional and native fishing (14.7) Protection of marine biodiversity spots in UGGp Active waste prevention and cleaning actions (14.1)
6 CLEAN WATER AND SANITATION	Ensure access to water and sanitation for all	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cooperation of your UNESCO Global Geopark with water companies Support of cleaning water activities & systems (6.3) Support of water-related ecosystems (e.g. in mountains, forests, rivers, lakes, groundwater) (6.6) 	15 LIFE ON LAND	Sustainably manage forests, combat desertification, halt and reverse land degradation, halt biodiversity loss	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Activities of your UNESCO Global Geopark to protect and restore ecosystems Protection of soil, prevent erosion, support biodiversity, preserve genetic resources awareness rising (15.1, 15.3, 15.6) Cooperation with forestry (e.g. planting activities with climate-resistant trees) (15.2) Activities to protect biodiversity (e.g. nesting houses, flowering areas, insect-friendly environment) (15.5) Protection of primary and secondary biotopes (often abandoned quarries) Protection and conservation of geosites and their geological & biological values Public gardening activities for local communities
7 AFFORDABLE AND CLEAN ENERGY	Ensure access to affordable, reliable, sustainable and modern energy for all	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use of sustainable energy in your UNESCO Global Geopark organisation Support of sustainable energy projects in your UNESCO Global Geopark communities Cooperation with innovative energy companies If available: E-drive team cars 	16 PEACE, JUSTICE AND STRONG INSTITUTIONS	Promote just, peaceful and inclusive societies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Capacity building activities with your UNESCO Global Geopark communities and municipalities (16.7) Services and offers to strengthen the regional identity Regional networking and communication Promotion of the SDGs in the regional context Common projects for members and partners Cooperation across local and regional borders Cooperation with political decision makers Community participation following the "bottom up" approach Sound and transparent Geopark management with broad participation of local communities (16.6) Cooperation with volunteers and stakeholders
8 DECENT WORK AND ECONOMIC GROWTH	Promote inclusive and sustainable economic growth, employment and decent work for all	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cooperation with small local businesses in your UNESCO Global Geopark (8.4) Cooperation with tourism organisations & destinations (8.9) Provision of touristic infrastructure Geopark like trails, information panels, which can be used to develop offers. Cooperation with partners, which follow sustainable rules related employment and environment Cooperation with local action groups for regional sustainable development 	17 PARTNERSHIPS FOR THE GOALS	Revitalize the global partnership for sustainable development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Information on the SDGs in your UNESCO Global Geopark (e.g. website, social media, magazines, brochures, workshops, campaigns) Your contributions to international networking of the UNESCO Global Geoparks via GGN (17.6) Your participation in common projects and activities of the UNESCO Global Geoparks and respective regional networks (e.g. workshops, courses, media, publications, UN days) Active cooperation between UNESCO Global Geoparks inside countries and across the continents by common projects (17.16, 17.17) Your contributions to capacity building and consultancy for potential UNESCO Global Geopark candidates (17.9) International networking between different UNESCO programmes by common projects (17.6) Promotion of the SDGs in the international context and publication of best practice (e.g. at conferences)
9 INDUSTRY, INNOVATION AND INFRASTRUCTURE	Build resilient infrastructure, promote sustainable industrialization and foster innovation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cooperation with public transport in your UNESCO Global Geopark (9.1) Consideration of public transport options to reach trails and activities Implementation and restoration of trail and information facility infrastructure Infrastructure and offers for people with special needs Cooperation with research and sciences (9.5) Own research activities 			

Global Geoparks Network SDG Working Group

UNESCO Global Geoparks Actions on SDG's in 2023

For 20 years now and all over the world, UNESCO Global Geoparks have campaigned for a holistic understanding of our planet and its evolution.

UNESCO Global Geoparks are areas of significant geological, natural, and cultural value that focus on the sustainable management of natural resources, education, and social development.

Their operations align with the core principles of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), as they promote environmental protection, local economic enhancement, and social equity.

Through activities such as environmental education, sustainable tourism development, and strengthening local cultural identity, UNESCO Global Geoparks contribute to a holistic approach supporting sustainability.

The Global Geoparks Network, their international network is an opportunity for exchanging ideas with partners around the world.

The integration of UNESCO Global Geoparks' shared values with the SDGs is achieved through preserving natural and cultural heritage, advancing scientific knowledge, and raising community awareness about the need to protect the planet.

UNESCO Global Geoparks serve as model territories for sustainable development, highlighting the importance of collaboration among scientific, cultural, and social stakeholders. They foster active community involvement, incorporating practices that contribute to long-term prosperity and ecological balance.

In accordance with their potentials, UNESCO Global Geoparks have been actively pursuing the Global Agenda 2030 with the 17 SDGs for a number of years. Their bottom-up approach with community participation and capacity building, their sustainable regional development activities as well as their networking from regional to international level make the UNESCO Global Geoparks ideal places to understand the relevance of the SDGs and also the responsibility of their implementation.

Thus the UNESCO Global Geoparks provide ideal model territories for implementing the Agenda 2030. They form the decisive interface between international declarations of intent and concrete on-the-spot activities – which means the transformation from strategy to action.

The Global Geoparks Network established the GGN Working Group on SDG's with the involvement of representatives from all regional geopark networks with main aim to strengthen the implementation of the Agenda 2030 with the 17 SDGs in its overall context and to communicate the active and supporting role of the UNESCO Global Geoparks, their philosophy, operation and daily tasks in this context.

SDGS
WORKING GROUP

The UNESCO Global Geoparks implementing SDG's

The 2023 Report on the implementation of SDG's

The GGN Working Group on SDG's organized and coordinated an online survey in order to present the contribution of the UNESCO Global Geoparks with various activities on the implementation of the goals. The GGN Working Group worked for the development of SDG template with basic information and examples of SDG implementation in UNESCO Global Geoparks.

The survey was supported by a series of SDG workshops in 2024 on the global and regional network level as well as by a tutorial. This procedure will be continued annually.

The UNESCO Global Geoparks were invited to answer an online questionnaire. The questionnaire included questions for each SDG separately. The questions focussed on actions, which are implemented by each UNESCO Global Geopark that promote each goal.

129 UNESCO Global Geoparks participating in the SDG's 2023 Report out of the total number of 178 UNESCO Global Geoparks (recognized in 2023).

The participated Geoparks are listed below:

Araripe UNESCO Global Geopark, Brazil	Grutas del Palacio UNESCO Global Geopark, Uruguay
Adamello Brenta UNESCO Global Geopark, Italy	Guangwushan-Nuoshuihe UNESCO Global Geopark, China
Alxa Desert UNESCO Global Geopark, China	Gunung Sewu UNESCO Global Geopark, Indonesia
Apuan Alps UNESCO Global Geopark, Italy	Hakusan Tedorigawa UNESCO Global Geopark, Japan
Aras UNESCO Global Geopark, Iran (Islamic Republic of)	Hantangang River UNESCO Global Geopark, Republic of Korea
Arxan UNESCO Global Geopark, China	Harz . Braunschweiger Land . Ostfalen UNESCO Global Geopark, Germany
Aso UNESCO Global Geopark, Japan	Haute Provence UNESCO Global Geopark, France
Bakony-Balaton UNESCO Global Geopark, Hungary	Hexigten UNESCO Global Geopark, China
Batur UNESCO Global Geopark, Indonesia	Holy Cross Mountains UNESCO Global Geopark, Poland
Beaujolais UNESCO Global Geopark, France	Hong Kong UNESCO Global Geopark, China
Geo-Naturpark Bergstrasse-Odenwald UNESCO Global Geopark, Germany	Huangshan UNESCO Global Geopark, China
Bohemian Paradise UNESCO Global Geopark, Czechia	Idrija UNESCO Global Geopark, Slovenia
Buzău Land UNESCO Global Geopark, Romania	Ijen UNESCO Global Geopark, Indonesia
Caçapava UNESCO Global Geopark, Brazil	Itoigawa UNESCO Global Geopark, Japan
Catalunya Centrla UNESCO Global Geopark, Spain	Izu Peninsula UNESCO Global Geopark, Japan
Chablais UNESCO Global Geopark, France	Jeju Island UNESCO Global Geopark, Republic of Korea
Chelmos-Vouraikos UNESCO Global Geopark, Greece	Jingpohu UNESCO Global Geopark, China
Ciletuh-Palabuhanratu UNESCO Global Geopark, Indonesia	Jiuhuashan UNESCO Global Geopark, China
Cliffs Of Fundy UNESCO Global Geopark, Canada	Kefalonia-Ithaca UNESCO Global Geopark, Greece
Comarca Minera UNESCO Global Geopark, Mexico	Keketuohai UNESCO Global Geopark, China
Dak Nong UNESCO Global Geopark, Vietnam	Kula-Salihli UNESCO Global Geopark, Türkiye
Danxiashan UNESCO Global Geopark, China	Kütralkura UNESCO Global Geopark, Chile
De Hondsrug UNESCO Global Geopark, Netherlands (Kingdom of the)	Land Of Extinct Volcanoes UNESCO Global Geopark, Poland
Djerdap UNESCO Global Geopark, Serbia	Langkawi UNESCO Global Geopark, Malaysia
Dong Van Karst Plateau UNESCO Global Geopark, Vietnam	Las Loras UNESCO Global Geopark, Spain
El Hierro UNESCO Global Geopark, Spain	Lauhanvuori-Hämeenkangas UNESCO Global Geopark, Finland
Famenne-Ardenne UNESCO Global Geopark, Belgium	Lavretotiki UNESCO Global Geopark, Greece
Fangshan UNESCO Global Geopark, China	Leiqiong UNESCO Global Geopark, China
Funiushan UNESCO Global Geopark, China	Lesvos island UNESCO Global Geopark, Greece
Geomôn UNESCO Global Geopark, United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland	Leye Fengshan UNESCO Global Geopark, China
Granada UNESCO Global Geopark, Spain	
Grevena-Kozani UNESCO Global Geopark, Greece	

Lushan UNESCO Global Geopark, China	Rocca Di Cerere UNESCO Global Geopark, Italy
Magma UNESCO Global Geopark, Norway	Rokua UNESCO Global Geopark, Finland
Maiella UNESCO Global Geopark, Italy	Saimaa UNESCO Global Geopark, Finland
Massif Des Bauges UNESCO Global Geopark, France	Salpausselkä UNESCO Global Geopark, Finland
Mëllerdall UNESCO Global Geopark, Luxembourg	Sar'in Kaigan UNESCO Global Geopark, Japan
Merangin Jambi UNESCO Global Geopark, Indonesia	Sanqingshan UNESCO Global Geopark, China
Mixteca Alta UNESCO Global Geopark, Mexico	Shennongjia UNESCO Global Geopark, China
Mount Kunlun UNESCO Global Geopark, China	Shilin UNESCO Global Geopark, China
Mourne Gullion Strangford UNESCO Global Geopark, United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland	Sierras Subbéticas UNESCO Global Geopark, Spain
Mt. Apo UNESCO Global Geopark, Japan	Southern Canyons Pathways UNESCO Global Geopark, Brazil
Mudeungsan UNESCO Global Geopark, Republic of Korea	Stonehammer UNESCO Global Geopark, Canada
Muroto UNESCO Global Geopark, Japan	Styrian Eisenwurzen UNESCO Global Geopark, Austria
Ngorongoro Lengai UNESCO Global Geopark, Tanzania	Tabas UNESCO Global Geopark, Iran (Islamic Republic of)
Ningde UNESCO Global Geopark, China	Taining UNESCO Global Geopark, China
Non Nuoc Cao Bang UNESCO Global Geopark, Vietnam	Taishan UNESCO Global Geopark, China
North Pennines UNESCO Global Geopark, United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland	TERRA.Vita UNESCO Global Geopark, Germany
Novohrad-Nógrád UNESCO Global Geopark, Hungary and Slovakia	Terras De Cavaleiros UNESCO Global Geopark, Portugal
Odsherred UNESCO Global Geopark, Denmark	Tianzhushan UNESCO Global Geopark, China
Oki Islands UNESCO Global Geopark, Japan	Toba Caldera UNESCO Global Geopark, Indonesia
Ore Of The Alps UNESCO Global Geopark, Austria	Toya - Usu UNESCO Global Geopark, Japan
Orígens UNESCO Global Geopark, Spain	Trollfjell UNESCO Global Geopark, Norway
Papuk UNESCO Global Geopark, Croatia	Troodos UNESCO Global Geopark, Cyprus
Platåbergens UNESCO Global Geopark, Sweden	Tumbler Ridge UNESCO Global Geopark, Canada
Pollino UNESCO Global Geopark, Italy	Unzen Volcanic Area UNESCO Global Geopark, Japan
Psiloritis UNESCO Global Geopark, Iran (Islamic Republic of)	Vestjylland UNESCO Global Geopark, Denmark
Qeshm Island UNESCO Global Geopark, Iran (Islamic Republic of)	Vikos-Aoos UNESCO Global Geopark, Greece
Qinling Zhongnanshan UNESCO Global Geopark, China	Vulkaneifel UNESCO Global Geopark, Germany
Quarta Colônia UNESCO Global Geopark, Brazil	Xiangxi UNESCO Global Geopark, China
Raja Ampat UNESCO Global Geopark, Indonesia	Xingwen UNESCO Global Geopark, China
Ries UNESCO Global Geopark, Germany	Yandangshan UNESCO Global Geopark, China
Rinjani-Lombok UNESCO Global Geopark, Indonesia	Yuntaishan UNESCO Global Geopark, China
	Zhangjiajie UNESCO Global Geopark, China
	Zhijindong Cave UNESCO Global Geopark, China
	Zigong UNESCO Global Geopark, China

Global Geoparks Network - SDG Working Group

UNESCO Global Geoparks

Actions on SDG's in 2023

Data statistic analysis

Key Observations for selected goals:

High Achievement Rates (>90 %): UNESCO Global Geoparks demonstrated notable success in organizing activities and promoting the following Goals:

Quality Education (SDG 4) Has the highest percentage of involvement and activities organization at 98.4%,

Decent Work and Economic Growth (SDG 8) at 94.5 %

Partnerships for the Goals (SDG 17) at 93. %.

Life on Land (SDG 15) UNESCO Global Geoparks made significant strides in environmental conservation, achieving **90 %** involvement with activities on the Goal

Moderate Achievement Rates (70-90 %):

Climate Action (SDG 13), **89%** involvement of UNESCO Global Geoparks underscoring their role in promoting biodiversity and addressing climate challenges.

This indicates that UNESCO Global Geoparks present a strong focus on fostering education, economic development, collaboration as well as life on land and climate action, which implies an ecological impact.

Lower Achievement Rates (>70 %): UNESCO Global Geoparks demonstrated quite successful involvement in Goals such as

Clean Water and Sanitation (SDG 6) activities by 67.2%of UNESCO Global Geoparks, respectively,

Affordable and Clean Energy (SDG 7) activities by 72% of UNESCO Global Geoparks, respectively, highlighting ongoing efforts but also areas for improvement.

Challenges in Achievement Rates: The lowest rate was observed in

Reduced Inequalities (SDG 10) with only 30.4% of UNESCO Global Geoparks participating with activities in this goal, reflecting the difficulty of addressing systemic social and economic disparities in certain regions.

Summary of Contributions:

UNESCO Global Geoparks effectively contribute to the Sustainable Development Goals through initiatives that combine conservation, education, and community development. They particularly excel in goals that align with their core values, such as education, innovation networking partnerships, community participation and environmental sustainability. However, there is room for improvement in addressing social disparities and inequalities to further align their activities with global development priorities.

NOTE

The Questionary was prepare and distributed by the GGN SDG's Working Group. Data collection and compilation E. Antonakis, UNESCO Chair on Geoparks and the sustainable development of insular and coastal areas, University of the Aegean, Greece Final assessment: GGN SDG's Working Group

Sustainable Development Goals		Number of UNESCO Global Geoparks with actions on the Goal	Percentage of UNESCO Global Geoparks with actions on the Goal
SDG 1	No Poverty	85	68%
SDG 2	End of hunger	99	76%
SDG 3	Good Health and well being	114	88%
SDG 4	Quality Education	127	98.4%
SDG 5	Gender Equality	108	83.7%
SDG 6	Clean Water sanitation	88	68.2%
SDG 7	Affordable and clean energy	94	72.8%
SDG 8	Decent work and economic growth	118	94.5%
SDG 9	Industry,innovation and infastructure	113	87.6%
SDG 10	Reduce inequillities	41	31.7%
SDG 11	Sustainable cities and communities	106	82%
SDG 12	Responsible consumption and production	110	85 %
SDG 13	Climate action	115	89 %
SDG 14	Life below water	72	55.8%
SDG 15	Life on land	117	90 %
SDG 16	Peace ,justice and strong institutions	107	83 %
SDG 17	Partnerships for goals	121	93.8%

Table 1 UNESCO Global Geoparks participating with activities in each goal

SDG Implementation by UNESCO Global Geopark 2023

Chart 1 Percentage of SDG's Achieved by UNESCO Global Geoparks

Horizontal bar chart, displaying the percentage of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) achieved by UNESCO Global Geoparks, sorted in ascending order of achievement. **The least achieved SDG appears at the bottom**, while the most achieved SDG is at the top. The color scheme remains consistent, highlighting performance levels:
Green: High involvement (above 90%).
Orange: Moderate involvement (70%-90%).
Red: Lower involvement (below 70%).

List of Geoparks participating with activities in each Goal

1 NO POVERTY

- Monitoring of risk areas near geosites as part of a geoconservation program.
- Organization of handicraft marketing and sales workshops
- Conducting entrepreneurship training workshops for local artisans
- Hosting local festivals, such as the Pomegranate Harvesting Festival, to promote local products.
- Donation of locally local products to food banks.
- Organizing rescue and safety workshops in disaster-prone areas.
- Providing grants to support sustainable tourism and local businesses.
- Creation of new job opportunities for unemployed young people in rural and remote areas
- Cooperation with women's cooperatives to promote local products.

Southern Canyons Pathways UNESCO Global Geopark, Brazil
Ciletuh-Palabuhanratu UNESCO Global Geopark, Indonesia
Dong Van Karst Plateau UNESCO Global Geopark, Vietnam
Hakusan Tedorigawa UNESCO Global Geopark, Japan
Jeju island UNESCO Global Geopark, Republic of Korea
Kütralkura UNESCO Global Geopark, Chile
Lesvos island UNESCO Global Geopark, Greece
Mëllerdall UNESCO Global Geopark, Luxembourg
Mixteca Alta UNESCO Global Geopark, Mexico
Novohrad-Nógrád UNESCO Global Geopark, Hungary and Slovakia
Raja Ampat UNESCO Global Geopark, Indonesia
Saimaa UNESCO Global Geopark, Finland
Salpausselkä UNESCO Global Geopark, Finland
Sanqingshan UNESCO Global Geopark, China
Shennongjia UNESCO Global Geopark, China
Toba Caldera UNESCO Global Geopark, Indonesia
Danxiashan UNESCO Global Geopark, China
Djerdap UNESCO Global Geopark, Serbia
El Hierro UNESCO Global Geopark, Spain
Guangwushan-Nuoshuihe UNESCO Global Geopark, China
Hexigten UNESCO Global Geopark, China
Hong Kong UNESCO Global Geopark, China
Keketuohai UNESCO Global Geopark, China
Kula-Salihli UNESCO Global Geopark, Türkiye
Las Loras UNESCO Global Geopark, Spain
Lauhanvuori-Hämeen kangas UNESCO Global Geopark, Finland
Leiqiong UNESCO Global Geopark, China
Massif des Bauges UNESCO Global Geopark, France

Merangin Jambi UNESCO Global Geopark, Indonesia
Ore of the Alps UNESCO Global Geopark, Austria
Rocca di Cerere UNESCO Global Geopark, Italy
Shilin UNESCO Global Geopark, China
Xiangxi UNESCO Global Geopark, China
Xingwen UNESCO Global Geopark, China
Odsherred UNESCO Global Geopark, Denmark
Sierras Subbéticas UNESCO Global Geopark, Spain
Adamello Brenta UNESCO Global Geopark, Italy
Alxa Desert UNESCO Global Geopark, China
Arxan UNESCO Global Geopark, China
Bohemian Paradise UNESCO Global Geopark, Czechia
De Hondsrug UNESCO Global Geopark, Netherlands (Kingdom of the)
Funiushan UNESCO Global Geopark, China
Haute Provence UNESCO Global Geopark, France
Idrija UNESCO Global Geopark, Slovenia
Jiuhuashan UNESCO Global Geopark, China
Maiella UNESCO Global Geopark, Italy
Mount Kunlun UNESCO Global Geopark, China
Ningde UNESCO Global Geopark, China
Pollino UNESCO Global Geopark, Italy
Qeshm Island UNESCO Global Geopark, Iran (Islamic Republic of)
Qinling Zhongnanshan UNESCO Global Geopark, China
Tianzhushan UNESCO Global Geopark, China
Trollfjell UNESCO Global Geopark, Norway
Tumbler Ridge UNESCO Global Geopark, Canada
Vulkaneifel UNESCO Global Geopark, Germany
Yandangshan UNESCO Global Geopark, China
Zhangjiajie UNESCO Global Geopark, China
Catalunya Centrla UNESCO Global Geopark, Spain
Famenne-Ardenne UNESCO Global Geopark, Belgium

Granada UNESCO Global Geopark, Spain
Grutas Del Palacio UNESCO Global Geopark, Uruguay
Leye Fengshan UNESCO Global Geopark, China
Lushan UNESCO Global Geopark, China
Ries UNESCO Global Geopark, Germany
Rinjani-Lombok UNESCO Global Geopark, Indonesia
Zigong UNESCO Global Geopark, China
Apuan Alps UNESCO Global Geopark, Italy
Gunung Sewu UNESCO Global Geopark, Indonesia
Izu Peninsula UNESCO Global Geopark, Japan
Mt. Apoi UNESCO Global Geopark, Japan
Yuntaishan UNESCO Global Geopark, , China
Aso UNESCO Global Geopark, Japan
Dak Nong UNESCO Global Geopark, Vietnam
Huangshan UNESCO Global Geopark, China

Unzen Volcanic Area UNESCO Global Geopark, Japan
Comarca Minera UNESCO Global Geopark, Mexico
Holy Cross Mountains UNESCO Global Geopark, Poland
Ngorongoro Lengai UNESCO Global Geopark, Tanzania
Non nuoc Cao Bang UNESCO Global Geopark, Vietnam
Troodos UNESCO Global Geopark, Cyprus
Caçapava UNESCO Global Geopark, Brazil
Toya-Usu UNESCO Global Geopark, Japan
Itoigawa UNESCO Global Geopark, Japan
San'in Kaigan UNESCO Global Geopark, Japan
Rokua UNESCO Global Geopark, Finland
Tabas UNESCO Global Geopark, Iran (Islamic Republic of)
Quarta Colônia UNESCO Global Geopark, Brazil
Mourne Gullion Strangford UNESCO Global Geopark, United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland

2 ZERO HUNGER

- Promotion of local food production through farmer markets and food fairs
- Supporting local farmers with training on organic farming practices. Las Loras
- Organizing culinary workshops to reduce food waste and promote sustainable gastronomy.
- Encouraging traditional farming practices, including crop rotation and organic fertilizers.
- Support for local cooperatives and small farmers through marketing initiatives.
- Geopark School Lunch held on 1st Wednesday of each month at local elementary and middle schools

Hantangang River UNESCO Global Geopark, Republic of Korea
Taishan UNESCO Global Geopark, China
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3 GOOD HEALTH AND WELL-BEING

- Environmental education campaigns focusing on waste management and clean air.
- Organizing health and wellness activities, including yoga and outdoor recreation.
- Conducting educational programs for children on disaster risk reduction.
- Developing recreational geotrails to promote physical activity and mental well-being.
- Supporting local health initiatives through partnerships with healthcare providers.
- Developing and providing hiking, cycling and other sportive activities.

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4 QUALITY EDUCATION

- Developing educational materials on geology, natural disasters, and conservation.
- Conducting workshops for students on environmental and cultural heritage.
- Collaborating with universities to offer field trips and research opportunities.
- Organizing education for sustainable development programs for schools to promote awareness of biodiversity and local heritage
- Promoting digital learning through the creation of educational videos and resources.
- Supporting teacher training programs to improve knowledge of local geology and biodiversity.

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5 GENDER EQUALITY

- Promoting women-led businesses through training and capacity-building workshops.
- Supporting women's associations to develop and market local products
- Ensuring gender-inclusive participation in geopark activities and decision-making.
- Offering leadership programs for women in local communities
- Creating employment opportunities for women through geotourism and hospitality.

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6 CLEAN WATER AND SANITATION

- Implementation of water conservation programs in local communities. Conducting workshops on efficient water management practices.
- Installing eco-friendly sanitation systems in geopark facilities.
- Promoting awareness campaigns about water pollution and conservation.
- Supporting the development of community water supply projects.
- Providing training on sustainable water use for agriculture.

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7 AFFORDABLE AND CLEAN ENERGY

- Installing renewable energy systems in geopark facilities.
- Promoting the use of solar panels and energy-saving technologies.
- Conducting workshops on energy efficiency for local businesses and residents.
- Raising awareness on the importance of reducing energy consumption.
- Partnering with local authorities to implement energy-saving initiatives

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8 DECENT WORK AND ECONOMIC GROWTH

- Creating job opportunities through geotourism and sustainable businesses
- Supporting local entrepreneurs with training and funding
- Promoting fair trade practices in local communities
- Organizing career development workshops for young people
- Encouraging sustainable economic practices in local businesses
- Partnering with local governments to promote inclusive economic growth

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Stonehammer UNESCO Global Geopark, Canada

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Non Nuoc Cao Bang UNESCO Global Geopark, Vietnam

Aras UNESCO Global Geopark, Iran (Islamic Republic of)

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Rokua UNESCO Global Geopark, Finland

9 INDUSTRY, INNOVATION AND INFRASTRUCTURE

- Developing sustainable infrastructure projects in geoparks.
- Promoting innovation in geoproducts and services
- Supporting research and development in sustainable technologies.
- Establishing partnerships with universities and research institutions.
- Encouraging local businesses to adopt innovative practices.
- Providing technical support for infrastructure projects in rural areas.

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Oki Islands UNESCO Global Geopark, Japan

10 REDUCED INEQUALITIES

- Promoting social inclusion programs in local communities
- Supporting vulnerable groups through education and training.
- Providing grants to support marginalized communities.
- Partnering with NGOs to address inequality issues.

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- Itoigawa** UNESCO Global Geopark, Japan

11 SUSTAINABLE CITIES AND COMMUNITIES

- Promoting sustainable urban planning practices.
- Supporting the development of eco-friendly infrastructure.
- Encouraging the use of public transportation and green mobility solutions.
- Organizing community events to raise awareness about sustainability.
- Collaboration with UNESCO WHS and other programmes

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12 RESPONSIBLE CONSUMPTION AND PRODUCTION

- Promoting sustainable consumption practices in local communities.
- Supporting local businesses in adopting eco-friendly production methods.
- Encouraging the use of sustainable materials in local products.
- Raising awareness about the environmental impact of consumption.
- Partnering with local authorities to implement waste management programs

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Comarca Minera UNESCO Global Geopark, Mexico

13 CLIMATE ACTION

- Conducting climate change awareness campaigns.
- Supporting local communities in developing climate adaptation plans.
- Promoting the use of renewable energy sources to reduce emissions.
- Organizing tree-planting campaigns to combat deforestation.
- Providing training on disaster risk reduction and emergency response.

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Lavretotiki UNESCO Global Geopark, Greece

14 LIFE BELOW WATER

- Supporting marine conservation projects in coastal geoparks.
- Conducting workshops on sustainable fishing practices.
- Promoting awareness about the importance of marine biodiversity.
- Partnering with local communities to reduce marine pollution.
- Supporting the development of eco-tourism activities focused on marine life.
- Raising awareness about the impact of climate change on marine ecosystems

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15 LIFE ON LAND

- Promoting biodiversity conservation in geopark areas.
- Conducting workshops on sustainable land management practices.
- Supporting the protection of endangered species in geoparks
- Partnering with local communities to promote reforestation projects.
- Raising awareness about the importance of preserving natural habitats.
- Organizing educational programs on the value of biodiversity.

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Caçapava UNESCO Global Geopark, Brazil

16 PEACE, JUSTICE AND STRONG INSTITUTIONS

- Promoting community participation in local decision-making processes.
- Supporting initiatives that strengthen local governance.
- Encouraging transparency and accountability in geopark management
- Partnering with local authorities to promote human rights and justice.
- Raising awareness about the importance of peaceful and inclusive societies.

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Saimaa UNESCO Global Geopark, Finland
Salpausselkä UNESCO Global Geopark, Finland
Sanqingshan UNESCO Global Geopark, China
Shennongjia UNESCO Global Geopark, China
Toba Caldera UNESCO Global Geopark, Indonesia
Odsherred UNESCO Global Geopark, Denmark
Trollfjell UNESCO Global Geopark, Norway
TERRA.Vita UNESCO Global Geopark, Germany
TERRA.Vita UNESCO Global Geopark, Germany
Jingpohu UNESCO Global Geopark, China
Danxiashan UNESCO Global Geopark, China
Djerdap UNESCO Global Geopark, Serbia
El Hierro UNESCO Global Geopark, Spain
Guangwushan-Nuoshuihe UNESCO Global Geopark, China
Hexigten UNESCO Global Geopark, China
Hong Kong UNESCO Global Geopark, China
Keketuohai UNESCO Global Geopark, China

Lauhanvuori-Hämeenkanas UNESCO Global Geopark, Finland
Leiqiong UNESCO Global Geopark, China
Massif Des Bauges UNESCO Global Geopark, France
Merangin Jambi UNESCO Global Geopark, Indonesia
Rocca Di Cerere UNESCO Global Geopark, Italy
Shilin UNESCO Global Geopark, China
Xiangxi UNESCO Global Geopark, China
Xingwen UNESCO Global Geopark, China
Xingwen UNESCO Global Geopark, China
Geomôn UNESCO Global Geopark, United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland
Pollino UNESCO Global Geopark, Italy
Mount Kunlun UNESCO Global Geopark, China
Qeshm Island UNESCO Global Geopark, Iran (Islamic Republic of)
Zhijindong Cave UNESCO Global Geopark, China
Rinjani-Lombok UNESCO Global Geopark, Indonesia
Izu Peninsula UNESCO Global Geopark, Japan
Terras De Cavaleiros UNESCO Global Geopark, Portugal
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Vestjylland UNESCO Global Geopark, Denmark
Mt. Apoi UNESCO Global Geopark, Japan
De Hondsrug UNESCO Global Geopark, Netherlands (Kingdom of the)
Tumbler Ridge UNESCO Global Geopark, Canada
Magma UNESCO Global Geopark, Norway
Araripe UNESCO Global Geopark, Brazil
Catalunya Centrla UNESCO Global Geopark, Spain
Unzen Volcanic Area UNESCO Global Geopark, Japan
Langkawi UNESCO Global Geopark, Malaysia
Oki Islands UNESCO Global Geopark, Japan
Muroto UNESCO Global Geopark, Japan

Bakony-Balaton UNESCO Global Geopark, Hungary
Órigens UNESCO Global Geopark, Spain
Kula-Salihli UNESCO Global Geopark, Türkiye
Las Loras UNESCO Global Geopark, Spain
Ore Of The Alps UNESCO Global Geopark, Austria
Vulkaneifel UNESCO Global Geopark, Germany
Ries UNESCO Global Geopark, Germany
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Grevena-Kozani UNESCO Global Geopark, Greece
Bohemian Paradise UNESCO Global Geopark, Czechia
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Arxan UNESCO Global Geopark, China
Funiushan UNESCO Global Geopark, China
Ningde UNESCO Global Geopark, China
Qinling Zhongnanshan UNESCO Global Geopark, China
Tianzhushan UNESCO Global Geopark, China
Yandangshan UNESCO Global Geopark, China
Zhangjiajie UNESCO Global Geopark, China

Apuan Alps UNESCO Global Geopark, Italy
Geo-Naturpark Bergstrasse-Odenwald UNESCO Global Geopark, Germany
Mudeungsan UNESCO Global Geopark, Republic of Korea
Granada UNESCO Global Geopark, Spain
Grutas del Palacio UNESCO Global Geopark, Uruguay
Zigong UNESCO Global Geopark, China
Harz . Braunschweiger Land . Ostfalen UNESCO Global Geopark, Germany
Styrian Eisenwurzen UNESCO Global Geopark, Austria
Psiloritis UNESCO Global Geopark,
Yuntaishan UNESCO Global Geopark, China
Buzău Land UNESCO Global Geopark, Romania
Huangshan UNESCO Global Geopark, China
Ngorongoro Lengai UNESCO Global Geopark, Tanzania
North Pennines UNESCO Global Geopark, United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland
Platåbergens UNESCO Global Geopark, Sweden
Holy Cross Mountains UNESCO Global Geopark, Poland
Vikos-Aoos UNESCO Global Geopark, Greece
Lushan UNESCO Global Geopark, China
Gunung Sewu UNESCO Global Geopark, Indonesia
San'in Kaigan UNESCO Global Geopark, Japan
Rokua UNESCO Global Geopark, Finland
Itoigawa UNESCO Global Geopark, Japan
Beaujolais UNESCO Global Geopark, France

17 PARTNERSHIPS FOR THE GOALS

- Global, Regional and National networking among UNESCO Global Geoparks
- International, Regional and National Geopark Conferences, Workshops and Events
- Capacity building activities - Supporting knowledge-sharing initiatives between Geoparks.
- Establishing partnerships with local, national, and international organizations
- Promoting collaborative projects to achieve sustainability goals.
- Organizing networking events for geopark stakeholders
- Partnering with universities and research institutions for joint studies.
- Encouraging cross-sector collaborations to address sustainability challenges

Hantangang River UNESCO Global Geopark, Republic of Korea
Taishan UNESCO Global Geopark, China
Southern Canyons Pathways UNESCO Global Geopark, Brazil
Ciletuh-Palabuhanratu UNESCO Global Geopark, Indonesia
Dong Van Karst Plateau UNESCO Global Geopark, Vietnam
Hakusan Tedorigawa UNESCO Global Geopark, Japan
Jeju Island UNESCO Global Geopark, Republic of Korea
Kütralkura UNESCO Global Geopark, Chile
Lesvos island UNESCO Global Geopark, Greece
Mëllerdall UNESCO Global Geopark, Luxembourg
Mixteca Alta UNESCO Global Geopark, Mexico
Novohrad-Nógrád UNESCO Global Geopark, Hungary and Slovakia
Raja Ampat UNESCO Global Geopark, Indonesia
Saimaa UNESCO Global Geopark, Finland
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Funiushan UNESCO Global Geopark, China
Idrija UNESCO Global Geopark, Slovenia
Jiuhuashan UNESCO Global Geopark, China
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Lushan UNESCO Global Geopark, China
Gunung Sewu UNESCO Global Geopark, Indonesia
Beaujolais UNESCO Global Geopark, France
Haute Provence UNESCO Global Geopark, France
Toya - Usu UNESCO Global Geopark, Japan
Aso UNESCO Global Geopark, Japan
Chelmos-Vouraikos UNESCO Global Geopark, Greece
Cliffs Of Fundy UNESCO Global Geopark, Canada
Ijen UNESCO Global Geopark, Indonesia
Taining UNESCO Global Geopark, China
Famenne-Ardenne UNESCO Global Geopark, Belgium
Leye Fengshan UNESCO Global Geopark, China
Papuk UNESCO Global Geopark, Croatia
Comarca Minera UNESCO Global Geopark, Mexico
Caçapava UNESCO Global Geopark, Brazil
Batur UNESCO Global Geopark, Indonesia
Itoigawa UNESCO Global Geopark, Japan
Tabas UNESCO Global Geopark, Iran (Islamic Republic of)
San'in Kaigan UNESCO Global Geopark, Japan
Rokua UNESCO Global Geopark, Finland
Quarta Colônia UNESCO Global Geopark, Brazil

Summary

UNESCO Global Geoparks have contributed in 2023 substantially to the SDGs with predominantly high to moderate achievement. Due to the continuous SDG workshops for the GGN and the continental networks, the GGN SDG Working Group expects advanced knowledge of the SDGs by the Geoparks in 2024 and the following years. As constantly new Geoparks become members of the IGGP, the education on SDGs and their role for the UNESCO Global Geoparks and how they can contribute will be an ongoing task. UNESCO Global Geoparks with their bottom-up approach have the power to support projects directly on site, which make the difference and bring the benefit of the SDGs to the people of their communities. The documentation of this impact can show how successful UNESCO Global Geoparks contribute to the SDGs.

<p>1 NO POVERTY</p>	<p>2 ZERO HUNGER</p>	<p>3 GOOD HEALTH AND WELL-BEING</p>	<p>4 QUALITY EDUCATION</p>	<p>5 GENDER EQUALITY</p>	<p>6 CLEAN WATER AND SANITATION</p>
<p>7 AFFORDABLE AND CLEAN ENERGY</p>	<p>8 DECENT WORK AND ECONOMIC GROWTH</p>	<p>9 INDUSTRY, INNOVATION AND INFRASTRUCTURE</p>	<p>10 REDUCED INEQUALITIES</p>	<p>11 SUSTAINABLE CITIES AND COMMUNITIES</p>	<p>12 RESPONSIBLE CONSUMPTION AND PRODUCTION</p>
<p>13 CLIMATE ACTION</p>	<p>14 LIFE BELOW WATER</p>	<p>15 LIFE ON LAND</p>	<p>16 PEACE, JUSTICE AND STRONG INSTITUTIONS</p>	<p>17 PARTNERSHIPS FOR THE GOALS</p>	

SDGS
WORKING GROUP